

Thursday, March 24, 2016 5:43:45 AM

#	Query	Limiters/Expanders	Last Run Via	Results
S4	S1 AND S2 AND S3	Search modes - Find all my search terms	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - PsycINFO	4
S3	((DE "Exercise" OR DE "Movement Therapy" OR DE "Physical Therapy" OR TX (exercise OR physical N3 therapy OR physiotherapy OR pilates OR (((muscle N3 strength) OR resistance OR balance) N3 (training OR therapy))))	Search modes - Find all my search terms	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - PsycINFO	76,054
S2	T1 (((motor N3 control) OR (neuromuscular N3 control) OR (motor N3 skill) OR (cognit* N3 motor) OR (cognitive N3 trunk) OR feedback OR (swiss N3 ball)) N6 (training OR exercise* OR therapy OR rehabilitation OR mov*)) OR T1 ((cognit* OR propriocept* OR coordinative OR voluntary OR deliberat* OR intentional* OR willful OR wilful OR purpose* OR designed OR planned OR intended) N6 (training OR exercise* OR therapy OR rehabilitation OR mov*)) OR T1 (sensorimotor OR sensorymotor OR	Search modes - Find all my search terms	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - PsycINFO	76,838

(sensory N3 motor) OR videogames
 OR exergames OR "dual task" OR
 proprioception OR (coordinat* N3
 muscle*) OR AB (((motor N3 control)
 OR (neuromuscular N3 control) OR
 (motor N3 skill) OR (cognit* N3
 motor) OR (cognitive N3 trunk) OR
 feedback OR (swiss N3 ball)) N6
 (training OR exercise* OR therapy OR
 rehabilitation OR mov*)) OR AB
 ((cognit* OR propriocept* OR
 coordinative OR voluntary OR
 deliberat* OR intentional* OR willful
 OR wilful OR purpose* OR designed
 OR planned OR intended) N6 (training
 OR exercise* OR therapy OR
 rehabilitation OR mov*)) OR AB
 (sensorimotor OR sensormotor OR
 (sensory N3 motor) OR videogames
 OR exergames OR "dual task" OR
 proprioception OR (coordinat* N3
 muscle*))

S1

((((DE "Abdomen") OR (DE
 "Thorax")) OR (DE "Back (Anatomy)")
 OR TX (torso OR trunk OR back OR
 abdomen OR pelvis OR thorax))
 AND TX (muscle N3 strength OR
 ((muscle N3 composition) AND
 (balance OR "functional performance"
 OR (falls AND (association OR
 relationship OR correlation)))))) OR TX
 (trunk OR core OR postural) N3

Search modes - Find all my search
 terms

Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases 50
 Search Screen - Advanced Search
 Database - PsycINFO

(strenght* OR stabili*) AND ((MH
"Aged+") OR TX ((aged OR elder*)
N3 (person* OR patient* OR man OR
men OR woman OR women OR
people)))